

STYLES AND CHARACTERISTICS OF RESIDENTIAL PREMISES OF THE MEDIEVAL PERIOD.

Kholmatov Furkatjon Sirojiddin ugli.

Master student at Namangan State University, Uzbekistan

Abstract. This article tells about the construction of a residence in the Middle Ages, its improvement, construction methods and urban planning traditions. At the beginning of the 9th-13th centuries, on the territory of Uzbekistan, the residences of rich and prosperous citizens consisted of an inner and outer courtyard, and rooms were formed around the courtyard. In such dwellings, kitchens, verandas, living rooms, corridors, utility and utility rooms stood out. Below is the detailed information about them.

Key words: rooms, outer yard, inner yard, saki, middle ages, residence.

By the early Middle Ages, the first stage of the construction of settlements on the territory of Uzbekistan was completed. These traditions, which began to form from the Bronze Age, are clearly visible in every part. By the beginning of the Middle Ages, separate hotels appeared in the homes of middle-class citizens and wealthy aristocrats, who made up the bulk of the cities. The walls of these hotels and the corridors leading to them are decorated with paintings. In the houses of wealthy aristocrats, wall paintings are painted with ganch on several plasters, and in middle-class houses sometimes directly on the "flower plaster". Similarly, in the houses of the wealthy class, access to the upper floor of the house is through a wide ramp, and in the houses of the middle class, a staircase is used. In addition, burnt bricks began to be used in the residences of representatives of the wealthy class, as well as in palaces and temples. Even in the villages, castles and fortifications, characteristic of the townspeople, were formed, consisting of separate complexes such as farms, gatherings, and hotels.

In cities, it was customary to have dwellings with two different layouts. In the first order, the rooms were interconnected, and according to the plan, a hotel was located at the end of the residence or next to it. The residences of this order are described by specialists as "elbow-plan residences". In the second order, the residences consist of parallel rooms of almost the same structure, using a common corridor. Settlements of this order are conventionally referred to by archaeologists as "comb-type settlements". By the Middle Ages, there were some changes in the construction of settlements as a result of the spread of a new ideology and religion. In addition, the establishment of centralized power plays an important role in this process. Now the main factor in the construction of residences is not to increase the defense capability, but to pay more attention to the interior of the residence. At the same time, courtyards began to form in

the settlements, which were preserved only in some cities (Dalvarzintepa) in antiquity and were almost never found due to age conditions in the early Middle Ages. The residences preserved the system of premises formed in the courtyard, as well as the system of "comb-planned residences". The system consisting of "rooms formed around a courtyard" is similar to the "elbow-shaped rooms" that developed in the hotel atro of the early Middle Ages.

its appearance has changed, and now the hotel in the form of a large hall is replaced by a courtyard. Dwellings of the second type ("dwellings of the comb plan") were discovered and studied at the 47th excavation site of Samarkand. The living quarters are located on the east and west sides of a long comb-shaped corridor. The fact that the walls of the rooms on the east side were 1 m thick allowed the researchers to conclude that the house was two-story.

The second dwelling discovered in this excavation belongs to the first type ("Elbow-shaped dwellings"), and the premises are located around a courtyard lined with burnt bricks. In the yard, between two rooms, there was a square platform 47-50 cm high and 2.5_x_2.5 in size, and experts came to the conclusion that this place looked like an ajar porch.

At the beginning of the 9th-13th centuries, on the territory of Uzbekistan, the residences of rich and prosperous citizens consisted of an inner and outer courtyard, and rooms were formed around the courtyard. In such dwellings, kitchens, verandas, living rooms, corridors, utility and utility rooms stood out. In most cases, the dwellings of this layer were two-story. Also, some residential buildings in the city have inner and outer courtyards, and household appliances (oven, stove, etc.) can be seen in the inner courtyard, and production equipment in the outer courtyard.

In general, we can say that in the formation of important parts of the settlements studied in ancient times on the territory of Uzbekistan, a number of features and common features are observed. Placement basis. In the Central Asian building culture, buildings are usually built on foundations. Firstly, a solid base made it possible to level the relief of the construction site; secondly, the walls of the building are damaged by various natural disasters: pollution, earth kept from shaking. In addition, the foundation has another function - to give glory to the building. Therefore, very high foundations were chosen for the palace of the rulers. Such foundations also protected the palace, which was a special fortress of the ruler, from destruction. The main building material for Tagkursi was straw and raw brick. If we pay attention to the foundations made of raw brick, then they say that this method has the most ancient basis and that such foundations are observed in almost all archaeological sites on the territory of

Uzbekistan, including the Dzharkoton and Chust sites. The Bronze Age can reach In particular, the foundation of the Jarkoton temple was built from 10 rows of raw brick up to 1.4 m thick. This tradition continued in the Iron Age, and the 2-meter foundation of the structure, recorded during the 1st excavation of the Koktepe site, was made of raw brick. Varakhsha, a well-studied monument of the Western Sogd of the early Middle Ages, uses a completely unique style of Thai carving on a mud brick base. This tradition was recorded during the study of the fortress. The Varakhshi Palace was originally built with solid parallel walls made of mud bricks, and the space between them was filled with broken bricks and mud bricks. Such a backfill is filled in the form of separate layers 25-30 cm thick. Thus, a solid foundation is laid. In the construction of residential buildings, together with mud brick foundations, foundations stronger than straw are used. Today we can see that pakhsa tagkursi began to spread widely from the early Iron Age. In particular, powerful pakhs foundations were studied at the sites of Kuchuktepa, Bandikhon, Pishaktepa, Kirhujra. By the early Middle Ages, it can be observed in almost all rural areas and castle fortifications, except for cities. In particular, during studies carried out in the layers of Samarkand dating back to the early Middle Ages, such a pakhs foundation was noted in many excavations. For example, on the eastern side of the monument, on the site of the current Museum of the History of Samarkand, at a depth of 6 m, the remains of a settlement dating back to the early Middle Ages were recorded. When clearing and studying the building of the 5th-7th centuries. it turned out that it was restored on a foundation 1 m high. Such a foundation was also noted at the famous 23rd excavation site, where the "Ikhshid Palace" was found. By the early Middle Ages, pakhs foundations were used more widely. This is noted by many researchers. According to them, during the period of large-scale construction in the city at the end of the 6th - beginning of the 7th century, in order to make room for new buildings, the builders made wide, high foundations from straw and shaped straw. . So, in ancient times, during the construction of residential buildings on the territory of Uzbekistan, the following types of building foundations were noted:

1. The base of monolithic straw or "straw blocks".
2. The foundation is entirely made of raw bricks
3. Foundation of straw and raw bricks together
4. The walls are made of mud bricks and straw, and damp soil is laid between them.

foundation prepared by compaction.

Foundation. The foundation did not become widespread until the early Middle Ages. Only

recorded only in some excavations. The oldest remains of such a foundation are recorded in the layers of the Afrosiab site dating back to the 8th century. By the Middle Ages, foundations of this type were widespread. In particular, the foundation of the Mausoleum of the Samonites in Bukhara has a depth of 2.3 m and is made of bricks. The bricks in the bottom three rows were 60_x_60_cm. The walls of the "reception hall" of the palace of the Termez rulers of the XI-XII centuries. built of raw bricks, and the foundation - of 10 rows of burnt bricks. In the same way, the brick foundation was laid for the mausoleum of Sultan Saodat in Old Termez. By the 14th and 15th centuries, complex foundations became widespread. In particular, the foundations of the Bibikhanum and Aksaroi mosques are made of stone.

So, the following types of foundations are distinguished:

1. From raw brick;
2. From baked bricks;
3. From stones (Fig. 14).

Walls. On the territory of Uzbekiston, straw and raw brick, which are the main building materials in architecture, were used very skillfully. Several methods were used in the construction of residential walls.

According to research, each construction method has its own function and reasons. In particular, despite the fact that walls made of solid straw are thick and strong, it took a long time to build a wall. After all, there is a special order and rules for the construction of a straw wall, that is, it is built layer by layer, and when the first floor is completed, it is necessary to build the second floor. Therefore, the builders took a long time. In addition, a thatched wall is often built where there is soil. The second method was to mark the straw using special forms (method 2).

Since the breeze easily passed between the molded straw blocks, they dried out much faster. At the same time, molded straw is resistant to various natural disasters and earthquakes. As a result of natural disasters, large cracks formed in the monolithic thatched walls. And since the dumps were built separately, the cracks did not cover the entire wall. This allowed such walled houses to be operated for a long time with easy repairs.

By the early Middle Ages, the location of the cities of the Sogdian civilization on an important trade route led to their rapid development. As a result, trading factories (addresses) and colonies of the Sogdians appeared not only in the Sogd regions, but also in Ustrushene, Tashkent, Ettisuva, East Turkestan, and later even in China and Silla (Korea) and other state territories. was The development of trade allowed the development of all industries, and in the VI-VII centuries, 2-3-storey houses were the

main part of the residences in the cities of Sogd. The builders paid more attention to the strength of the building wall.

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